

Synthesis of Some Trifluoromethylphenazines

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Synthesis and properties of several trifluoromethylphenazines containing the acenaphthene, isatin and phenanthrene nuclei have been reported.

ACENAPHTHAPHENAZINES, indophenazines and phenanthraphenazines have been studied principally as dyes¹⁻¹⁰. Isatin and its derivatives have been found to be associated with antiviral¹¹, antibacterial¹², anthelmintic¹³ and hypotensive¹⁴ activity. Again biological activity of indophenazines¹⁵⁻¹⁹ and their use as optical bleaches²⁰ has also received attention, whereas phenanthraphenazines have been found to possess both anticancer and cancer inducing properties^{21,22}.

Study of halogen containing phenazines is meagre²³ and no study appears to have been directed to phenazines containing fluorine atom, although a variety of fluorine containing compounds have been observed to show significant biological activity²⁴⁻²⁸. A series of investigations on fluorine containing phenazines have, therefore, been presently undertaken in our laboratory (partly reported)²⁹. In this communication we report about acenaphthaphenazines(I), indophenazines(II) and phenanthraphenazines(III) all of which contain three fluorine atoms forming a trifluoromethyl group attached to the benzenoid ring at position 2 or 3.

These phenazines have been prepared by the condensation of 4-trifluoromethyl-*o*-phenylenediamine³⁰, with

- acenaphthenequinone and its 3-chloro-, 3-bromo- and 3 : 4-dinitro-derivatives to yield compounds of type I.
- isatin and its 5-bromo-, 5-chloro-, 5-nitro-, 5-iodo-, 5 : 7-dibromo- and 5-bromo-7-nitro-derivatives to produce phenazines of the type II and
- phenanthraquinone and its 2-nitro- and 2 : 7 dinitro-derivatives to give compounds of the type III.

These condensations in general occur smoothly. The acenaphthaphenazines and phenanthraphenazines are yellow whereas the indophenazines are yellow to deep yellow (with the exception of Sl. No. 5 which forms greenish silky needles from ethyl acetate). Theoretical possibility of the production of structural isomer exists in a few cases, but it was observed that one isomer was predominantly produced which could be obtained in a pure state.

The phenazines reported here could not be developed well on wool and do not appear to be of much value as dyestuffs. All the above phenazines are soluble in methanol, ethanol, ethyl acetate, chloroform, benzene, pyridine and nitrobenzene. Details about the colour, yield, solvent of crystallisation are given in the Table. Biological assay of a few selected compound is proposed to be undertaken.

Experimental

The diketone was first dissolved in minimum volume of boiling glacial acetic acid and then molar proportion of 4-trifluoromethyl-*o*-phenylenediamine was added, and refluxing was continued. The resulting phenazines were thrown out of the solution immediately in most cases but the mixture was kept

TABLE 1—ISATIN=I; ACENAPHTHENEQUINONE=AQ; PHENANTHRAQUINONE=PQ; INDOPHENAZINES=IP; ACENAPHTHAPHENAZINE=AP; PHENANTHRAQUINONE=PP, 4-TRIFLUOROMETHYL-O-PHENYLENEDIAMINE=TOP

Sl. No.	Reactants	Name of the Product	Appearance solvent	M.P. °C %yield of crude	Molecular formula	Colouration with conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Analysis of Nitrogen Required	Found
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1.	AQ+TOP	2-Trifluoromethyl AP	Light yellow Pyridine	280-81 90	C ₁₀ H ₉ F ₃ N ₂	Brownish yellow	8.69	8.81
2.	3-Chloro-AQ+TOP	2-Trifluoromethyl-8-(or-9) Chloro AP	Light Brown Ethylacetate	179-80 98	C ₁₀ H ₈ ClF ₃ N ₂	Red	7.85	8.12
3.	3-Bromo-AQ+TOP	2-Trifluoromethyl-8-(or-9) bromo AP	Light yellow Ethylacetate	174-75 81	C ₁₀ H ₈ BrF ₃ N ₂	Bright red	6.98	7.14
4.	3:4-Dinitro-AQ+TOP	2-Trifluoromethyl-8:9-dinitro AP	Brownish yellow Ethylacetate	243-44 100	C ₁₀ H ₇ F ₃ N ₂ O ₄	Yellow	7.29	7.41
5.	I+TOP	2-(or-3)Trifluoromethyl IP	Parrot green Ethylacetate	294-95 65	C ₁₅ H ₈ N ₃ F ₃	Reddish-brown	14.63	15.11
6.	5-Chloro-I+TOP	2-(or-3) Trifluoromethyl-9-chloro IP	Yellow needles Methanol	272-73 62	C ₁₅ H ₇ ClF ₃ N ₃	Deep-brown	13.02	13.25
7.	5-Bromo-I+TOP	2-(or-3) Trifluoromethyl-9-bromo IP	Yellow needles Methanol	281-82 80	C ₁₅ H ₇ BrF ₃ N ₃	Deep-brown	11.48	11.51
8.	5-Iodo-I+TOP	2-(or-3) Trifluoromethyl-9-iodo IP	Brownish yellow Ethylacetate	315-17 48	C ₁₅ H ₇ F ₃ IN ₃	Deep-brown	10.169	10.24
9.	5-Nitro-I+TOP	2-(or-3) Trifluoromethyl-9-nitro IP	Deep-orange Pyridine	329-30 95	C ₁₅ H ₇ F ₃ N ₄ O ₂	Deep-orange	16.86	17.12
10.	5:7-Dibromo-I+TOP	2-(or-3) Trifluoromethyl 7:9-dibromo IP	Orange Acetic acid	296-97 72	C ₁₅ H ₆ Br ₂ F ₃ N ₃	Yellow	9.44	9.53
11.	5-Bromo-7-Nitro-I+TOP	2-(or-3) Trifluoromethyl-7-nitro-9-Bromo IP	Orange Acetic acid	278-79 100	C ₁₅ H ₆ BrF ₃ N ₄ O ₂	Orange	13.63	13.82
12.	PQ+TOP	2-Trifluoromethyl PP	Dull green Ethylacetate	184-85 88	C ₉ H ₁₁ F ₃ N ₂	Scarlet red (Bright)	8.045	8.13
13.	2-Nitro-PQ+TOP	2-Trifluoromethyl-7-(or-12)-nitro PP	Deep yellow Pyridine	272-73 43	C ₉ H ₁₀ F ₃ N ₂ O ₂	Chocolate-brown	10.69	10.81
14.	2:7-Dinitro-PQ+TOP	2-Trifluoromethyl-7:12-dinitro PP	Pale-yellow Pyridine	320-21 88	C ₉ H ₉ F ₃ N ₄ O ₄	Orange	12.79	13.11

boiling for 5-10 mins, to ensure complete reaction. After cooling, the solids were removed by filtration, washed and crystallised from appropriate solvent.

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